

RESIN TRANSFER PRESSING – A NOVEL PROCESS FOR LARGE SCALE COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

A new composite manufacturing process, „Resin Transfer Pressing“ (RTP), is introduced in this paper. In this process, nonwoven fabrics (NWFs) made of recycled carbon fibers (rCFs), are oversaturated with thermoset resin, i.e. they contain excess resin. The oversaturated NWFs are prefabricated and used as resin carrier in a press process, where they are placed in a heated mold together with a dry textile-based preform. During pressing, the resin is pressed out and transferred from the NWFs into the unimpregnated preform and hence impregnates the whole reinforcement. In this study the basic functionality of the process is investigated, which means that the oversaturation of NWFs and the RTP laminate manufacturing are investigated.

In order to quantify the ability of a nonwoven to be oversaturated with resin, the saturation degree (SDE) is introduced and different glass fiber (GF) and rCF based NWFs are assessed. SDEs of up to factor 12 for GF NWFs and up to factor 60 for rCF NWFs were determined. Different laminates are manufactured by RTP and the impregnation quality is evaluated via microscopic cross-sections. With an optimized stacking sequence a pore content < 1% was achieved at a combined (preform plus NWF) fiber volume content of 35%. If oversaturated NWFs made of recycled carbon fibers (rCFs) are used to impregnate a laminate made of virgin glass fibers, the NWF content of the final part can (but must not) be minimized to 2.1% (SDE = 15).

1 INTRODUCTION

The demand for carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRPC) is recording significant growth, which, according to a study by Carbon Composites e. V., can be estimated at 10% - 13% p.a. in the coming years up to 2022. This corresponds to a global demand for carbon fibers (CF) of 117 kt for the year 2022. [1]

Despite ongoing research to reduce carbon fiber CF waste during the production of CFRPC, still up to 30% of CF ends up as waste during manufacturing processes, e.g. as scrap parts or textile cut-off waste. Especially the cut-off wastes are suitable for a recycling, since fibers are still free of resin and equipped with the original sizing [2, 3].

The challenge therefore is to find suitable solutions for the reintegration of the cut-off waste, ideally by reintegrating it into the original manufacturing process. This would correspond to a zero-waste manufacturing philosophy and is seen to be an ideal concept on how to deal with manufacturing scrap.

A novel approach on the development of an according process to manufacture rCFRPC (partially) out of manufacturing cut-off wastes is suggested in this paper in order to prospectively fulfill the requirements for a zero-waste manufacturing. The foreseen manufacturing process is called Resin Transfer Pressing (RTP) and is based on so-called oversaturated nonwoven fabrics (NWF) made of rCF.

The RTP process exploits the specific advantages of nonwoven fabrics (NWFs) made of recycled carbon fibers (rCFs), such as the capability to store a large amount of resin. The rCF NWFs are initially oversaturated with a thermoset resin and thus contain a resin amount which outmatches the

NWFs weight by far. The NWFs are then used as semi-finished products and placed in a press tool together with a dry textile preform. When the press tool closes, the excess resin in the NWFs is transferred into the preform (cf. Figure 1). Efficiency and robustness of such an impregnation through the thickness of a preform is proven to be suitable for large volume manufacturing by processes such as Wet Compression Molding (WCM) [4, 5].

Figure 1: Process chain for resin transfer pressing.

The objective of the present study is to proof the basic functionality of the RTP process in general. A requirement of the RTP process is the ability of NWFs to be oversaturated with resin. Hence, the saturation degree (SDE) will be introduced and different NWFs will be characterized.

Sample plates will then be manufactured with the RTP process and analyzed regarding their impregnation quality by the use of micrographs and gray-scale analysis.

Expected process advantages are:

- Flexibility in laminate design due to variable rCF content
- Robust process due to standardized semi-finished products
- Economic efficiency due to incorporation of in-house manufacturing waste (“closed loop”)

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Materials

The fast-curing thermoset Epoxy resin system Hexion TRAC 06150 with an internal release agent has been used for the experiments. The properties of the Epoxy system are summarized in Table 1.

	Temperature	Unit	Value
Pot life	25 °C	min	120 ± 10
Gel time	120 °C	s	150 ± 30
Viscosity at room temperature	25 °C	mPa*s	8,000
Viscosity after 60/120/180 s	120 °C	mPa*s	40/865/>100,000
Curing time	120 °C	s	ca. 300

Table 1: Manufacturing properties of Hexion TRAC 06150 system [6]

A glass fiber (GF) non-crimp fabric (NCF) from Saertex of the type X-E-444 g/m² was used as dry preform. For preliminary experiments, GF NWFs with different areal weights (30 g/m², 225 g/m², 300 g/m² and 450 g/m²) were used. The rCF NWF used for flat laminate manufacturing has been

developed by the company Wagenfelder Spinnereien GmbH. It featured a nominal areal weight of 80 g/m² and consisted of 70 wt.-% rCF and 30 wt.-% PA6 fibers. The rCFs (type Toray® T620) used for the manufacturing of the NWFs was derived from manufacturing cut-offs emerging in the serial production of CFRPC parts at the project partner ACE Advanced Composite Engineering GmbH. The used textiles are summarized in Table 2.

		NCF	M1	M2	M3	GF-NW	rCF-NW
Textile type		Non-crimp-fabric	Mat	Mat	Mat	NWF	NWF
Fiber type		GF	GF	GF	GF	GF	rCF/PA6
Fiber partition	wt.-%	-	-	-	-	-	70/30
Areal weight	g/m ²	444	225	300	450	30	80
Fiber (mix) density	g/cm ³	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	~1.5
Orientation		± 45 °	isotrop.	isotropic	isotropic	isotropic	isotropic
Manufacturer		Saertex	PD FG	PD FG	PD FG	R&G	Wagenfelder Spinnereien

Table 2: Used fiber-based textiles.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Saturation tests

Technical and economical meaningfulness of RTP is directly correlated to the relation of NWFs and oriented reinforcement in the final part, in our case cut rCF NWFs in relation to continuous virgin fiber (GF-NCF) preform. For a high performance, the rCF-fraction should be minimized, which again requires that NWFs can store a high amount of resin. To quantify the capability to store resin, the saturation degree (SDE) was defined as the ratio of resin mass to NWF mass.

$$SDE = \frac{m_{resin}}{m_{NWF}} \quad (1)$$

In the target process for the oversaturation of NWFs by a thermoset impregnation machine, the NWF is unwound on a resin film on a transport foil. Also there is the option to cover the NWF with a second resin film from above. This process was simulated on lab-scale. For the determination of the maximum possible SDE of the different NWFs in these two cases (single- and double-sided impregnation), dry samples of the size 25 x 25 cm² were weighed and then placed in a basin with resin for 180 s without pressure (saturation time) (cf. **Figure 2**). Afterwards, the saturated sample was placed on a steel grid for 180 s (drip-off time), so that fluid dripped off until a steady SDE is established. The sample was then weighed again and SDE was calculated. In a second test series, samples were turned around after 90 of 180 s saturation time (in a resin basin as well as on a steel grid) to simulate a second resin film covering the NWFs in the real process.

Figure 2: Phases of determining the SDE for NWF.

The nomenclature of the tested specimens is given in **Figure 3**. A selection of nine different combinations of the factors fiber type, textile area weight, impregnation style and fluid were investigated.

Figure 3: Description of specimen nomenclature.

2.2.2 Plate manufacturing

Suitable process parameters were identified for the used resin system in preliminary work and are shown as process diagram in **Figure 4**. In order to fit the viscosity curve of the used resin, a two-stage pressure profile was used. In the first stage, a low pressure of 7 bar is applied for 30 s in order to avoid resin racing on the stack surface. Then a high pressure of 56 bar is applied for the residual curing time. This set of process parameters has been used for all further laminates described in this paper.

Figure 4: Process parameters for laminate manufacturing

Different stack set-ups were used to manufacture flat laminates with the materials stated in Table 2. The resin amount was kept constant for all laminates; the top layers therefore had different SDEs.

First, a reference flat laminate was produced by using the WCM process. The stack consisted of three layers of NCFs without any top layers. The resin was applied directly on the NCF, the mold was closed and the pressing cycle was started. During the pressing process, the excess resin was transferred from the top layer into the stack and impregnated the fibers.

Then, different GF-based NWFs were used to produce flat laminates by RTP. In this case, the top layers were over-saturated, the bottom layer was dry. In a third series, rCF NWFs were used for the RTP process. Finally, two different stack set-ups with rCF-NWF were investigated. In the first version (rCF-NW-1S), only the top layer was over-saturated, the bottom layer was dry. In a second set-up (rCF-NW-2S), also the bottom layer was oversaturated with resin, the total resin amount was split on the two layers (top and bottom). Three flat laminates of each set-up have been manufactured.

All set-ups are summarized in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Manufactured stack set-ups

For all manufactured flat laminates, pore and fiber volume content (FVC) was assessed by gray scale analysis. Three specimens of each set-up were produced and analyzed. All measurements were repeated three times for statistical validation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Saturation tests

The reciprocal density of NWFs has been found to correlate with the containing potential of the dry NWFs and can be used as an indicator for the ability of a NWF to be oversaturated. The reciprocal density ρ_r (in cm^3/g) is calculated by equation 2, where m_{areal} is the areal weight of the dry NWF and h_{NWF} is the height of the dry NWF (without compaction).

$$\rho_r = \frac{h_{NWF}}{m_{areal}} \quad (2)$$

For the group of single-side impregnated NWFs with oil as test-fluid the reciprocal density and resulting SDEs correlate to 89.5%. If Resin is used as test fluid, the two factors correlate

at a rate of 94.0%. For the group of double-sided impregnated NWFs the reciprocal density correlates with the SDE at 98.9%.

Furthermore, for fluids with higher viscosity, a double-sided impregnation is favorable since the fiber materials tend to float on the fluid during the relevant process time, which causes a mediocre oversaturation in the case of a single-sided impregnation. With a double-sided impregnation, the NWFs sink when they are turned over after 90 seconds. Also, the through-thickness impregnation is generally facilitated since the impregnation distance is halved in the case of a double sided impregnation. The SDE can be multiplied 3 to 4 times by a double-sided impregnation compared to single-sided.

Finally, it can be stated that the rCF NWFs outperforms all GF NWFs by far. This can be attributed to the fact that the reciprocal density of the rCF-NWFs is high compared to the GF NWFs. Furthermore, the reproducibility of the SDE measurements is fairly good, considering the manual experimental set-up. Figure 6 and **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** summarize the results.

		GF 225	GF 300	GF 450	GF 300	GF 300	GF 30	GF 30	rCF 80	rCF 80
		1S O	1S O	1S O	1S R	2S R	1S R	2S R	1S R	2S R
Saturation Degree (SDE)	Avg.	3.59	2.65	2.58	3.97	11.73	17.5	42.01	15.70	59.53
	SD	0.17	0.24	0.15	0.49	0.90	2.3	7.3	1.20	3.30
Reciprocal density	cm ³ /g	26.7	20.0	13.3	20.0	20.0	100	100	124.3	124.3

Table 3: SDE values for different NWF types and fluids

Figure 6: Saturation degrees (SDEs) for different NWF types and fluids

3.2 Plate manufacturing

The laminate impregnation quality of the different set-ups in general showed satisfying results. Pore contents ranged from 0.33% up to 3.82% (cf. Table 4). The reference laminate showed the best result in pore content with 0.33%.

Regarding the GF-based set-ups, the pore contents for GF-NW and 3x-GF-NW are < 1%. These set-ups used one respectively three 30 g/m² GF NWFs as top and bottom layers. These thin layers

showed a good capability to transfer their excess resin into the stack. In contrast to these results, 1x-M3 (450 g/m² mat) and 2x-M1 (2x 225 g/m² mats) showed significantly higher pore contents with 3.82% and 1.58%, respectively. Micrographs show that the thick mats show a mediocre compaction behavior and therefore transfer less resin into the residual stack.

It can be concluded that thin layers show a better transfer behavior, but also provide a higher SDE, which further facilitates the resin transfer. It is desirable to use higher SDEs for the RTP process.

This conclusion is supported by the results for set-ups with rCF NWFs. An impregnation quality with a pore content of <1% could be achieved when the resin was split on the top and bottom layer, as it was the case for set-up rCF-NW-2S. For the single sided impregnation, the pore content was 2.26% and therefore significantly higher.

The reference laminate's total FVC was 29.88%. The FVC of the other investigated set-ups correspond well to that FVC, since additional fiber material was brought into the set-up by using the over-saturated NWFs with different areal weights while the matrix amount was kept constant. In consequence, the FVCs of the other set-ups are higher. The corresponding micrographs are shown in Figure 7 and the quantitative results in Table 4.

Figure 7: Micrographs of laminate set-ups.

			Ref.	GF-NW	1x-M3	3x-GF-NW	2x-M1	rCF-NW-1S	rCF-NW-2S
Pore content (PC)	%	Avg.	0.33	0.78	3.82	0.58	1.58	2.26	0.74
		SD	0.16	0.37	1.39	0.56	0.48	0.68	0.66
Fiber vol. content (FVC)	%	Avg.	29.88	35.02	39.31	34.52	37.28	31.25	33.79
		SD	1.95	1.68	2.83	1.63	1.75	2.50	2.85

Table 4: Results for pore content and fiber volume content of investigated laminate set-ups.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The target of this study was to evaluate the feasibility of the resin transfer pressing (RTP) and the use of nonwoven fabrics oversaturated with resin, which is a requirement for the RTP process.

The results have shown that the concept of resin transfer pressing could be proven. For the oversaturation of nonwoven fabrics, a saturation degree SDE has been introduced. By investigating different GF and rCF nonwoven fabrics it could be shown that SDEs are in general high enough to impregnate dry preforms in the RTP process. Especially rCF-based nonwoven fabrics show a high SDE potential of up to 60.

Different laminate set-ups were manufactured in RTP and analyzed regarding the fiber volume content and pore content. It could be shown that the use of heavy mats, e.g. a 450 g/m² is not suitable for the production of high-quality laminates in RTP, since too much resin is hold back by the top layer. Especially a double-sided impregnation by oversaturating both the top and the bottom layer showed a good pore content, as it can be comprehended by the comparison between rCF-NW-1S (single-side impregnation) and rCF-NW-2S (double-side impregnation).

Future research will concentrate on the development of the RTP process from a proof-of-concept stage to the next level, e.g. the automatized oversaturation of nonwoven fabrics.

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